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UNMANAGED HONEY BEES EXPERIENCE
FROM CILENTO (SOUTH OF ITALY)

Esperienza con api non gestite nel Cilento (sud Italia)

Annual reports of bee colony mortality due to different environmental stressors, both biotic and abiotic, are still a big concern for the beekeeping industry. Nevertheless, several researchers have reported unmanaged populations of European honey bee colonies despite being infested with *Varroa* mites and, in turn, other pathologies.

It seems clear that the adaptation to the environmental condition leads to the feral status of the colonies with a high level of resilience. With the aim to understand differences in immune response between managed and unmanaged colonies a metagenomic analysis of worker honey bee gut will set up. The results could shed light on the gut bacteria involved in the bee immune response and be a start point for designing an efficient selection program for honey bee queens production.

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